

Impact of Demonetization on Bank Deposits and Advances of Scheduled Commercial Banks in India

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Abstract

After the Govt of India's sudden and shocky announcement of demonetization, Indian financial system stood stagnant for a long period, especially banking system. Banks are core part of any economy. They channelize money for the smooth functioning of different sectors in India. The major function of every bank is accepting deposits and lending loans. Growth pattern of deposit and lending is one of the important factors which affect the profitability and risk management of bank. The unexpected demonetization decision of ruling government has greatly influenced on the accepting and lending functions of entire banks in India, especially the scheduled commercial banks. This study mainly focuses on the short term impacts of demonetization on the growth rate of aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit i.e. advances of scheduled commercial banks. This study adopts a descriptive and analytical approach and the study is purely based on secondary data. Data were obtained from the annual, monthly and quarterly reports and various publications of RBI. During the study various websites, magazines, journals, newspapers and books dealing with the current banking scenario are also referred. The data used in the present analysis is confined from November 2015 to November 2018.

Keywords: demonetization, Indian Financial System, Bank Deposits and Advances, Scheduled Commercial Banks.

Introduction

The term 'Demonetization' is an unforgettable, widely debating and well experiencing term from November 8th 2016 till now. Every nook and corners of India, even every single person of India whether it is a politician, bureaucrat, business tycoon, banker, cheap jack, hawker, peddler, fisherman, grocer, farmer, laborer, housewife, child, etc has experienced the effect of demonetization. After the Govt of India's announcement of demonetization, Indian financial system stood stagnant for a long period, especially banking system. Banks are core part of any economy. They play vital role in the economic development and growth of the Nation. They channelize money for the smooth functioning of different sectors in India. The primary function of every bank is to accept deposits and grant loans. They act as the link between lenders and borrowers i.e. those who have

the money to those who needs the money. Growth pattern of deposit and lending is one of the important factors which affect the profitability and risk management of a bank. The unexpected demonetization decision of Modi Govt. has greatly influenced on the accepting and lending functions of entire banks in India especially, the scheduled commercial banks. While celebrating the second anniversary of phenomenal decision of demonetization, our Nation never completely wakeup from this tremendous currency confiscation. Nowadays every economy of India is trying to adjust with this historical moment of demonetization. It will take at least five to six years to get the complete and actual results of this demonetization. But today i.e. two years after the demonetization, only short-term effects are quite visible. This study mainly focuses on the short-term impacts of demonetization on the growth rate of aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit i.e. advances of scheduled commercial banks. This study adopts a descriptive and analytical approach and it is based on secondary data. Research period is from November 2015 to November 2018, it is a comparative study which considers pre and post demonetization period.

Concept of ‘Demonetization’, ‘Scheduled Commercial Banks’ and ‘Bank Deposits & Advances’

A. Demonetization

Demonetization is the act of stripping a currency unit of its status as legal tender. It is a process of removing a currency from general usage or circulation. Demonetization has happened thrice in India. The first was on the 12th January 1946, second on 16th January 1978 and third was on 8th November 2016. In November 2016, the Indian government demonetizes Rs.500 and Rs. 1000 notes valued at 15.4 trillion and constituting 86.9 per cent of the value of total notes in circulation and issued new Rs.500 and Rs.2000 currency notes in exchange for the discontinued ones. Ruling government’s main objective of this note ban is to eradicate counterfeit currency, resist tax evasion, destroy the black money and terrorist financing activities, and to encourage the country towards the cashless economy.

B. Scheduled Commercial Banks

The scheduled commercial banks are those banks which are included in the second schedule of RBI Act 1934 and which carry out the normal business of banking such as accepting deposits, giving out loans and other banking services. Banks not under this Schedule are called Non-Scheduled Banks. Scheduled Commercial Banks includes Public Sector Banks (SBI, Nationalized Banks, and IDBI), Private Sector Banks (old and new), Foreign Banks and Regional Rural Banks.

C. Bank Deposits and Advances-Primary function of banks

Accepting deposits and lending advances and loans are the primary function of banks.

Accepting Deposits

Banks collect and preserve surplus money from the public and they pay interest to them. The depositors are benefited and their amount of money is safe at the banks. In this situation, the banks can earn a sum of money on the amount collected by them. The banks create credit on the basis of deposits. The level of creation of credit depends upon the amount of deposits. Fixed deposits, current deposits, savings deposits and recurring deposit are the important type of bank deposits.

Lending advances and loans

The advances of bank may be granted in the form of loans, overdraft, cash credit, credit discounting bills of exchange. The bank advances loan more than the amount of deposits, because

all the loans are not withdrawn immediately. Therefore the loan creates deposits, while advancing loans; the bank gives priority to safety and next profitability. In advancing loans, the principles of investment safety, liquidity and profitability, diversification and social objectives are considered.

Demonetization's Short Term Impact on Bank Deposits & Advances

Demonetization is a generations' memorable experience and is going to be one of the economic events of our time. Its impact is felt by whole financial system of the Nation, of which banking system is the most affected one. Since the demonetization announcement came on 8th November 2016, each and every bank branches have been filled with customers. Day to day operations of entire banks in India was stagnant. Every banker has been trying to protect their bank as well as their customers. They had to manage their day to day operations with immense stress. During this period (November 2016) small and medium sectors were struggling to repay the loans. Majority of banks have stopped distributing micro credit to its customers. This means the credit disbursed earlier which was related to the same project or work is rendered useless, thus leading to rise in Non-Performing Assets. Likewise the sudden demonetization also affects the growth of bank credit and bank deposits as well. The growth trend of bank deposits move upwards and lending loans and advances (i.e. bank credit) move downwards. Demonetization made the banks to accept the deposits without any cost of promotion and it drastically increased liquidity position of the banks. The sudden demonetization results was there was an inflow of huge funds, increase in the number of customers, expansion of banking activities, increase in the volume of number of bank transactions, etc. But this trend took place only for a short period of time. At present i.e. two years after the momentous demonetization all these hectic conditions were tremendously changed and now everything back to normal.

Literature Review

Ambalika Sinha and Divya Rai (2016), the authors highlighted in their research paper titled "Aftermath of demonetization on rural population", the informal sectors of Indian economy where cashless transactions are minimal were the major sufferers of demonetization. Here they concentrated on the micro and macroeconomic effects of demonetization. Authors finally concluded that compared to macro economic effect, micro economic effects are more beneficial; why because of uncollected revenue increased & political move on terror financing was restrained. Whereas macro economic effect not beneficial due to the several problems faced by the people.

Balamurugan.S and Hemalatha.B.K (2016), the study entitled "Impacts on Demonetization: Organized and Unorganized Sector" researchers high lighted the short term as well as long term impact of demonetization on the various organized and unorganized sectors depending upon the extent of cash availability, credit availability, spending & government finances. Authors also opined that compared to small and tiny scale establishments, medium and large scale businesses are not much affected by note ban decision of govt. of India. They also emphasized that Small scale Establishments were deeply affected by demonetization.

Mayilsamy, R (2007), the study entitled "Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in short term cooperative credit structure- An Overview", he opined that the banks have to participate in recovery strategies and plan for recovery management. He also pointed that if banks are failed to manage the credit recovery, the huge burden of NPAS breaking the backbone of the short term co-operative credit structure in India.

Research Gap

From the above literature, it is found that only limited number of research has been conducted by combining demonetization effect and growth of bank deposits and gross bank credit of Scheduled Commercial Banks. It is very clear that no study has been focused on the growth trend of aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit of Scheduled Commercial Banks in India during pre and post period of demonetization. Most of the studies concentrated on impact of demonetization on the various organized and unorganized sectors, its effect on NPAs. Few studies have been conducted in the general impact of demonetization on economy with its short term and long term effects on banking sectors.

Significance of the Study

The present study titled “Demonetization and its effect on growth rate of bank deposits and advances: An analytical observation of Scheduled Commercial Banks in India” is an attempt to provide a clear picture of growth trend of bank deposits and bank credit of Scheduled Commercial Banks in India during pre and post demonetization period. This study mainly concentrated on comparing the growth trend of bank deposits and bank credit of entire Scheduled Commercial Banks during demonetization period and checking whether the growth trend moves upward or downward. For this, last few years’ (November 2015 to November 2018) growth trend of bank deposits and bank credit of Scheduled Commercial Banks in India were examined. If we want to understand the real progress or changes occurred in entire Indian banking system, it is enough to learn progress or changes occurred in Scheduled Commercial Banks. Scheduled Commercial Banks are the mirror image of entire banking system in India. Hope, present study will be a good reference to those who wants to know more about the immediate effect of demonetization (declared on November 8th 2016 -3rd demonetization of India) on the growth rate of aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit of scheduled commercial banks in India. Thus, the present study is relevant as per the prevailing scenario.

Objectives of the Study

To analyze and compare the growth trend of aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit i.e. advances of scheduled commercial banks in India during pre and post demonetization period.

Research Question

Does demonetization has any impact on the growth rate of aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit i.e. advances of scheduled commercial banks in India?

Research Framework

Research Methodology

The study is analytical and descriptive in nature. Information needed for the present study is obtained from various secondary sources. The present study is mainly based on secondary data obtained from the annual, monthly and quarterly reports, and various publications of RBI. During the study various websites, magazines, journals, newspapers and books dealing with the current banking scenario are also referred. The data used in the present analysis is confined from November 2015 to November 2018.

Result and Discussion

The present study mainly focus on the critical analysis of past and present trend of aggregate bank deposits as well as gross bank credit of scheduled commercial banks in India. For this, last few years’ (i.e. from November 2015 to November 2018) aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit of scheduled commercial banks in India were collected from annual, monthly, and quarterly reports, and various publications of RBI. With the help of these genuine periodical data, a true comparison between aggregate bank deposits of scheduled commercial banks from November 2015 to November 2018 was made. Likewise a true comparison between gross bank credits of scheduled commercial banks from November 2015 to November 2018 was also done.

Table 1: Aggregate bank deposits of scheduled commercial banks

Period	Aggregate bank deposits of scheduled commercial banks (In Billions)	Change (+/-) from the Base period	Change (+/-) from the previous period	Percentage Change (+/-) from the Base period
November 2015	90727.22	--	--	--
December 2015	91323.83	596.61	596.61	.658
January 2016	92182.73	1455.51	858.9	1.60
February 2016	92994.09	2266.87	811.36	2.50
March 2016	93272.9	2545.68	278.81	2.81
April 2016	95253.24	4512.02	1980.34	4.97
May 2016	95140.87	4413.63	-112.36	4.86
June 2016	95435.61	4708.39	294.74	5.19
July 2016	96219.07	5491.85	783.46	6.05
August 2016	96782.51	6055.29	563.44	6.67
September 2016	100936.5	10209.28	4153.99	11.25
October 2016	99317.89	8590.67	-1618.61	9.47
November 2016	104846.6	14119.38	5528.71	15.56
December 2016	104698.1	13970.88	-148.5	15.40
January 2017	104451.1	13723.88	-247	15.13
February 2017	104398.2	13670.98	-52.9	15.07
March 2017	107576.6	16849.38	3178.4	18.57
April 2017	105644.1	14916.88	-19325	16.44
May 2017	104995.6	14268.38	-6485	15.72
June 2017	107651.1	16923.88	2655.5	18.65
July 2017	106114	15386.78	-1537.1	16.96

August 2017	105937.1	15209.88	-176.9	16.76
September 2017	109175.4	18448.18	3238.3	20.33
October 2017	107975.5	17248.28	-1199.9	19.01
November 2017	107948.3	17221.08	-27.2	18.98
December 2017	109521.9	18794.68	1573.6	20.72
January 2018	109421.8	18694.58	-100.1	20.61
February 2018	109962.2	19234.98	540.4	21.20
March 2018	114260.5	23533.28	4298.3	25.94
April 2018	113814.2	23086.98	-446.3	25.45
May 2018	113528.2	22800.98	-286	25.13
June 2018	114982.2	24254.98	1454	26.73
July 2018	115298.7	24571.48	316.5	27.08
August 2018	116465.2	25737.98	1166.5	28.37
September 2018	117998.6	27271.38	1533.4	30.06
October 2018	117712.6	26985.38	-286	29.74
November 2018	119602.9	28875.68	1890.3	31.83

Source: Annual, Quarterly and Monthly statistical reports from RBI.

From the above table it is very clear that, the growth of aggregate bank deposits of scheduled commercial banks in India shows an upward trend, Month by month trend goes on increasing pace. On November, 2015 aggregate bank deposit shows Rs.90727.22 billion, but after one year i.e. November, 2016 it become Rs.104846.6 billion. On November, 2018 the rate increased from Rs.107948.3 billion (November, 2017) to Rs. 119602.9 billion that means compared to previous year i.e. November 2017, there has been additional increase of Rs.11654.6 billion. While comparing November, 2018th aggregate bank deposits of scheduled commercial banks with base year i.e. November, 2015 (Rs.90727.22 billion) there was an increase of at 28875.68 billion; which indicates a bombastic growth of bank deposits from previous years. When compared to previous periods, on October 2016 i.e. just one month before demonetization there was a negative trend in the growth of bank deposits (Rs.-1618.61billion). But on November 2016, during demonetization time, a great positive change in the growth of bank deposits of Scheduled Commercial Banks i.e. increase of Rs.5528.71 billion was visible, which was the highest change from the previous period in a decade. This is the notable surge in the growth of deposits arise in the recent banking era. From the base period there has been increase of Rs. 14119.38 billion, that means the percentage increase of Rs.15.56 billion. But after the demonetization bonanza, from December 2016 onwards there is a glimpse of negative trend in the growth of bank deposits from previous years. But on November 2018, from the base period there has been increase of Rs 28875.68 billion, that means the percentage increase of Rs. 31.83 billion. Hence, after comparing the growth of bank deposits, from the above table it is clearly found that there is a drastic surge occurred year after year in the aggregate growth of bank deposits. This will encourage the liquidity and profitability of entire banking system of India.

Table 2: Gross Bank credit of Scheduled Commercial Banks

Period	Gross Bank credit of scheduled commercial banks (In Billions)	Change (+/-) from the Base period	Change (+/-) from the previous period	Percentage Change (+/-) from the Base period
November 2015	68391.54	-	-	-
December 2015	69882.49	1490.95	1490.95	2.18
January 2016	70554.77	2163.23	672.28	3.16
February 2016	71447.78	3056.24	893.01	4.47
March 2016	72496.15	4104.61	1048.37	6.00
April 2016	72322.95	3931.41	-173.2	5.75
May 2016	72264.41	3872.87	-58.54	5.66
June 2016	72279.6	3888.06	15.19	5.68
July 2016	72405.48	4013.94	125.88	5.87
August 2016	72477.19	4085.65	71.71	5.97
September 2016	74948.68	6557.14	2471.49	9.59
October 2016	73844.14	5452.6	-1104.54	7.97
November 2016	72617.54	4226	-1226.6	6.18
December 2016	73173.91	4782.37	556.37	6.99
January 2017	73895.28	5503.74	721.37	8.05
February 2017	74588.5	6196.96	693.22	9.06
March 2017	78414.66	10023.12	3826.16	14.66
April 2017	75823.91	7432.37	-2590.75	10.87
May 2017	75694.58	7303.04	-129.33	10.68
June 2017	78198.07	9806.53	2503.49	14.34
July 2017	76702.19	8310.65	-1495.88	12.15
August 2017	76911.94	8520.4	209.75	12.46
September 2017	79834.38	11442.84	2922.44	16.73
October 2017	78846.45	10454.91	-987.93	15.29
November 2017	79347.15	10955.61	500.7	16.02
December 2017	81794.6	13403.06	2447.45	19.60
January 2018	81471.89	13080.35	-322.71	19.13
February 2018	82374.48	13982.94	902.59	20.44
March 2018	86254.25	17862.71	3879.77	26.12
April 2018	85176.25	16784.71	-1078	24.54
May 2018	85376.55	16985.01	200.3	24.83
June 2018	86728.07	18336.53	1351.52	26.81
July 2018	86162.27	17770.73	-565.8	25.98
August 2018	87807.53	19415.99	1645.26	28.39

September 2018	89816.64	21425.1	2009.11	31.33
October 2018	90339.75	21948.21	523.11	32.09
November 2018	92218.98	23827.44	1879.23	34.84

Source: Annual, Quarterly and Monthly statistical reports from RBI.

From the above table, it is found that, on November 2018, recorded its highest gross Bank credit of Rs 92218.98 billion from Rs 79347.15 billion by November 2017. From the base period there has been increase of Rs. 23827.44 billion, that means the percentage increase of Rs. 34.84 billion. While comparing pre-demonetization period with demonetization period (November 2016) there was a negative trend in the growth of bank credit i.e. decreases of Rs. 1226.6 billion occurred when compared to previous period. During this period banks were reluctant to lend advance or loans to their customers as the entire banking sector was stagnant. But after the demonetization, there glimpse a slow growth in the trend of bank deposits from previous years.

Findings and Conclusion

After analyzing the growth trend of aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit of scheduled commercial banks in India during pre and post demonetization period, it is found that, the surge in the growth of bank deposit during demonetization was temporary in nature; this trend was happened only for a short period of time. From the above analysis it is clearly understood that from the next month of demonetization i.e. December 2016, the unexpectedly created hike in the demand of bank deposit started to decline week by week and eventually went back to normal as pre demonetization period. While comparing growth trend of aggregate bank deposits and gross bank credit of scheduled commercial banks in India no drastic changes were found as per the above data during pre and post period of demonetization. Our Indian banking sector seems to be very strong because they can manage hectic unexpected situations within few months or years. This is a pleasant alarm to the sustainability of Indian banking sector. But in the case of gross bank credit of scheduled commercial banks, there found only minute slippage in lending function of banks. It is clearly identified that demonetization resulted heavy stress and work pressure for a lot of Small Scale Units as most of them depended on local sales through cash. During the period of demonetization, banks are reluctant to grant loans and advances to their customers' especially Small Scale Industrial customers' as the entire banking sector were stagnant. This hesitation comes into sight only for a short period of time, and then everything becomes normal.

While celebrating the second anniversary of demonetization, only several controversial talks, hot discussions and hectic debates on this area were found. Till now no one reached the final conclusion regarding the relevance of demonetization and its success and failure. At present i.e. two years after the demonetization, only short-term effects are quite visible. It will take at least five to six years to get the complete and actual results of this demonetization.

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